

A STUDY ON TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF MATHEMATICS TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Mathematics is one of the core subjects in secondary education different modern concepts and methods are introduced in the syllabus of mathematics at secondary stage. The curriculum revision is being undertaken by the state department of education (SCERT) and the central department of education (NCERT) constantly and all the modern mathematics is incorporated at the secondary stage. The teacher education programs for preparing mathematics teachers are also strength and during the past to ducats whenever the curriculum is changes different researching programs such as refresher courses, seminars, workshops etc., are conducted to make true teaching of mathematics more effective in secondary schools. Hence in this paper it is proposed to undertake teacher wise and student wise analysis for this study keeping in view of certain variables like gender, area of school, medium of teaching, board of school and teaching experience and a tool to measure teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers and also to understand the type of relationship between the teaching effectiveness. The collected is analyzed by inferential statistics. The results revealed no significant differences in mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards gender, area of school, medium of teaching, board of school and teaching experience.

Key Words: Mathematics Teachers, Distribution, Teaching

Introduction:

Education plays a vital role in giving human being for proper equipment to lead precious and harmonious life. The education is a purposely and organized activity which is undertaken both by educator and learner for the sake of clear objective. Education has widely discussed and interpreted by different thinkers, philosophers and educationists with reference to its aims functions and implications. The present study is proposed to analyze the teaching Effectiveness of math's teachers in relation to gender, area of school, medium of teaching, board of school and teaching experience teacher ratio and syllabus. Hence the purpose of the present study is to develop a tool to measure teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers and also to understand the type of relationship between the teaching effectiveness and its relation to student achievement.

Teaching Effectiveness:

In the dictionary of education BENGIMEN define teaching efficiency as the” Degree of success of a teacher in performing instructional and other duties specified in his position”. The teaching effectiveness of secondary school mathematics is measured by obtaining rating from both head of the instructions on overall rating on the efficiency of the teacher selected at random on

- Knowledge in the subject matter
- Interest in teaching
- Preparation for teaching
- Discipline skill in class management
- Clarity in expression
- Expertise in teaching methods
- Moral values
- General knowledge and common sense
- Enthusiasm in doing things and getting things done by the student
- Honesty and sincerity in work

Statistical Analysis:

As it was mentioned already a questionnaire was administered on mathematics teachers to obtain the data and relevant information concerning teaching mathematics. The data where carefully analyzed by employing appropriate statistical techniques was used. To test the different hypothesis “t-test” and “F-ratio” where employed appropriately.

Statement of the Problem:

A Study on Teaching Effectiveness of Mathematics Teachers

Sample Design:

In this study, the sampling unit was the teachers of teaching mathematics in Vellore district. The total size of the sample was 210. The samples were collected using random sampling technique. Out of the 210 samples, 92 male and 118 female teachers of teaching mathematics taken as sample of study.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out whether there is significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards gender.
- To find out whether there is significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards area of school.
- To find out whether there is significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards medium of teaching.
- To find out whether there is significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards area of board of school.
- To find out whether there is significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards teaching experience.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- There is no significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards gender.
- There is no significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards area of school.
- There is no significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards medium of teaching.
- There is no significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards area of board of school.
- There is no significant difference exists in the mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers towards teaching experience.

Tools Used For the Present Study:

- Teacher Effectiveness Scale by Umme Dixit (1993).

Description of the Tool and Scoring Procedure:

Preparation and planning for teaching classroom management, discipline, motivation, interaction, evaluation, knowledge of subject-matter its delivery and presentation including black board summary; teachers characteristics and interpersonal relations of teachers with others.

The scale is self-administrable. There is no time limit and there is no right or wrong responses. Hence the teachers are free to express their responses as they perceive, keeping in view the maximum possible effectiveness (high) of teachers and the least possible effectiveness (low) of teachers, as frame of references for individual rating. The scale had 60 statements. It is Likert type, scale range from poor, fair, good, very good and excellent. Score range from 1,2,3,4 and 5. Total score of the respondent ranges from 0 to 260.

Inferential Analysis:

Table 1: 't' test Between Mean Scores of Teaching Effectiveness of Mathematics Teachers Towards Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	92	145.36	46.11	1.002	NS
Female	118	152.05	49.32		

It is evident from the table 1 the calculated 't' value is 1.002, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.

Area of School and Teacher Effectiveness:

Table 2: 't' Test Between Mean Scores of Teaching Effectiveness of Mathematics Teachers Towards Area of School

Area of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	103	148.72	47.32	0.117	NS
Urban	107	149.50	48.76		

It is evident from the table 2 the calculated 't' value is 0.117, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.

Medium of Teaching and Teacher Effectiveness:

Table 3: 't' Test Between Mean Scores of Teaching Effectiveness of Mathematics Teachers Towards Medium of Teaching

Medium of Teaching	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
English	103	148.72	47.32	0.465	NS
Tamil	107	149.50	48.76		

It is evident from the table 3 the calculated 't' value is 0.465, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil medium of mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.

Board of school and Teacher Effectiveness:

Table 4: 'F' Test among the Sub- Samples of Board of School with Teaching Effectiveness of Mathematics Teachers Towards Medium of Teaching

Type of School	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1390.371	695.185	2	0.300	NS
Within Groups	479134.410	2314.659	207		
Total	480524.781		209		

It is evident from the table 4 the calculated 'F' value is 0.300, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of board of school with mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.

Teaching Experience and Teacher Effectiveness:

Table 5: 't' Test Between Mean Scores of Teaching Effectiveness of Mathematics Teachers Towards Medium of Teaching

Teaching Experience	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Less than 10 years	99	144.86	47.84	1.216	NS
Above 10 years	111	152.91	47.93		

It is evident from the table 5 the calculated 't' value is 1.216, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found between less than 10 years and above 10 years of mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.

Major Findings of the Study:

- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil medium of mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of board of school with mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found between less than 10 years and above 10 years of mean scores of teaching effectiveness of mathematics teachers.

Recommendations for Future Studies:

In this study, mathematics teachers' awareness of teacher effectiveness was assessed using a questionnaire, i.e., a self-report measure. Future studies could use alternative methods, both quantitative and qualitative. They could also measure the reality (level) of effective teaching practices and address the significance relationship between teaching effectiveness towards mathematics teaching. Finally, developing teaching models and strategies based on effective teaching would be valuable.

Conclusion:

The results also showed that there is no significant differences in mathematics teaching towards teaching effectiveness in the sample, which might be logical since new teachers in the transition to applied practice will have many questions about the most teaching effectiveness.. However, it may also be due to the lack of professional development programs for new teachers. As for the sample of teachers with ten or more years of experience, some need to be more motivated to develop their teaching effectiveness in line with modern trends and instead tend to use traditional teaching methods.

In contrast, teachers with 5-10 years of experience are more likely to know how to teach their students effectively. They may also be more motivated to develop their teaching methods because they know more about teaching practices, are aware of their students' levels. There were no differences in the gender, area of school, medium of teaching, board of school and teaching experience which is most likely because the emerging interest

in teaching effectiveness in recent years has resulted in all teachers, regardless of experience, being subject to the same guidelines and training programs, which include presenting the latest trends.

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